

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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BACK TO BASICS: IMPROVING PATIENTS' KNOWLEDGE AND SELF-
EFFICACY OF MEDICATION MANAGEMENT IN A PRIMARY CARE SETTING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Adverse drug events (ADEs) result in 700,000 emergency department (ED) visits annually and are often the result of medication nonadherence. Older adults are twice as likely as other age groups to experience an ADE leading to an ED visit and are seven times more likely to require hospitalization following such an event. Lack of knowledge regarding one's medication regimen can lead to dangerous medication errors. Most medication errors are avoidable with the implementation of simple interventions such as the use of a medication administration chart along with patient education in the primary care setting.

The purpose of this evidence-based project was to improve knowledge and self-efficacy of medication management among adults aged 65 and older in a primary care setting. Developing, implementing, and evaluating evidence-based activities to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy by encouraging self-management of medication regimens were specific aims of this project. Based on current evidence, older adults benefit from personal attention when receiving education regarding their medication regimens. Clear instructions accompanied by a concise, accurate medication list are effective at improving medication adherence and knowledge in the primary care setting.

Project participants' medication knowledge was evaluated using the Medication Knowledge Assessment Tool (MKAT) and levels of self-efficacy of medication management were assessed using the Self-Efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use Scale

(SEAMS) at baseline. Participants then received standardized education regarding their medication regimens, provision of a current medication list, encouragement to take their current medication list to all medical appointments, and a two-day follow up phone call to reinforce the education. Medication knowledge and self-efficacy of medication management were reassessed at one- and two-month intervals. Repeat education was provided following reassessment at each of the intervals. Aggregate mean scores of the MKAT and SEAMS at baseline, one-month, and two-months were compared.

At baseline, 34% of participants (N = 50) carried a medication list. After receiving education and follow up phone calls, the percentage increased to 68% and 88% (one- and two-months, respectively). Thus, there was a 158% increase from baseline to two-months. The increase was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 12.12, p = .000$). Participants' knowledge of their medications improved. The improvement was sustained at the two-month follow up at an average of 11%. Mean MKAT percentage scores rose from 79.38% at baseline to 85.24% and 88.12% at one- and two-months respectively. SEAMS scores showed only slight improvement of 2.73, 2.83, and 2.85 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively, yet these differences were statistically significant ($p = .000$).

The findings of the study support the use of standardized education in the primary care setting. Such education improved participants' medication knowledge and levels of self-efficacy of medication management. The "Back to Basics" approach increases medication safety among older adults.

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BACKGROUND

Problem Statement

Adverse drug events (ADEs) result in 700,000 emergency department (ED) visits annually (AHRQ, 2017) and are often the result of medication nonadherence (Lam & Fresco, 2015). Older adults are twice as likely as other age groups to experience an ADE leading to an ED visit. In fact, this population is seven times more likely than other age groups to require hospitalization following such an event (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2012). ADEs can occur due to medication omission, overuse, or misuse. The older adult population is of special interest since it is projected this population will double in number during the timeframe from 2005 to 2030. (Eldercare Workforce Alliance, 2018).

One of the reasons older adults are especially vulnerable to ADEs is the high number of medications prescribed to them (Mulhem et al., 2013). The majority of older adults take at least five prescription medications (Kwint, Stol, Faber, Gussekloo, & Bouvy, 2013) making their medication regimens more complicated than those of other patient populations. The number of medications taken on a daily basis frequently overwhelms the elderly population served by the principle author, with patients often making a choice to eliminate medications they believe are less important to their medication regimens.

Another major issue contributing to medication nonadherence among older adults is their lack of knowledge and casual attitudes regarding their medication regimens (Marek et al., 2013). Further complicating the problem is the issue of medication changes that occur as older adults experience multiple transitions in settings of care. Older adults

commonly receive prescriptions from multiple providers who do not communicate with each other, leading to conflicting medication lists. Patients served by the principle author see many specialists, resulting in frequent changes of medications. Often, patients lack the knowledge of which medications are a part of their current medication regimen leading to over and under use of prescription medications. Possessing accurate medication lists is of utmost importance to older adults to assist in successful medication management.

The majority of medication errors are avoidable with the implementation of simple interventions such as the use of a medication administration chart (Elliott, Lee, Beanland, Vakil, & Goeman, 2016). One basic intervention is to provide a clear list of medications with the medication name, dose, schedule, and purpose (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2012). Encouraging patients to self-manage their medication regimens will promote health self-efficacy and improved outcomes (Marek et al., 2013). In a world of advanced technology, the older patient responds more readily to a “back to basics” approach according to the principle author’s experience. The provision of a clear, accurate list of medications may seem a simplistic choice, but such a document is a tangible tool for this population allowing for self-management of their medication regimens.

Ideally, patients self-manage their medication regimens and alert their primary care physicians (PCPs) when medication changes occur. Nurses by virtue of their education and commitment to serve as care coordinators across settings are in a unique situation to develop, implement, and evaluate evidence-based interventions. Evidence-based interventions can address the issues contributing to decreased knowledge regarding

medication regimens among older adults. Implementation of such interventions will improve the quality of care provided to this population.

The “back to basics” approach to improving patients’ knowledge regarding medication regimens involves nursing education in its rudimentary form. Due to hearing and visual losses experienced by the older adult population, it is important to teach in an environment free from distraction where patients are able to ask questions (Sollitto, 2017). Providing a clear explanation regarding medications during one-on-one conversations along with a current medication list will ensure the transfer of consistent and complete information (Lee, Nishimura, Ngu, Tieu, & Auerbach, 2014). Patients need encouragement to call their primary care office for questions regarding their medication regimens. Patients who receive education from nurses have significantly better health over time (Meranius & Hammar, 2016). In the older population, simple nurse care coordination regarding medications is more successful than complicated, technological approaches (Marek et al., 2013).

Purpose of Project

The purpose of this evidence-based project was to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy of medication management among adults aged 65 and older in a primary care setting. The specific aims were to:

- Develop, implement, and evaluate evidence-based activities to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy by encouraging self-management of medication regimens
- Develop recommendations to improve knowledge about medication regimens and self-efficacy among older adults

Supporting Framework and Conceptual Model

Supporting frameworks and conceptual models guide doctorate of nursing practice projects (Polit & Beck, 2017). A conceptual approach provides structure and organization to a project (Roush, 2015). Both models and theories serve as a foundation upon which to format a proposal (Bonnel & Smith, 2014). The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) framework and Nola Pender's Health Promotion Model (HPM) served as the theoretical underpinnings for this DNP project.

The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) Model

The PDSA model, or cycle, is especially useful with healthcare related quality improvement initiatives. The PDSA model uses a systematic approach to initiate and evaluate a rapid cycle practice change (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017). Three specific questions associated with the PDSA model initiate the quality improvement process:

- “What are we trying to accomplish?”
- How will we know that a change is an improvement?
- What changes can we make that will result in improvement?” (IHI, 2017, p.1)

The four stages (Plan, Do, Study, and Act) associated with the PDSA model provided an outline to plan, implement, and evaluate this project (See Appendix A). A brief description of the PDSA framework follows.

Plan

Initially, the author answered the question: *What is the project trying to accomplish?* The purpose statement clearly defined the improvement of older patients' knowledge about their medication regimens as the author's goal. This stage involved

obtaining project approval, identifying stakeholders, forming a team, formulating goals, defining characteristics that qualify patients for inclusion in the project, and outlining which data to collect (The Deming Institute, 2018). The Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Long Beach, reviewed this project. Stakeholders consisted of the patients treated, the employees in the office where the project took place, and the primary practice team members. In this project, the team consisted of a physician (MD), a registered nurse (RN), and a medical assistant (MA). Though the RN (the principle author) conducted the majority of the data collection, the MD and MA provided support. Clearly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria for the project subjects were identified as well. The author ensured the team members were aware of the project's purpose.

Do

Once a plan was developed, the second stage in the cycle consisted of implementing the plan (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017). The author collected pre- and post-practice change data regarding medication knowledge and levels of self-efficacy of medication management. The implementation of patient-focused medication education commenced, including provision of a current medication list along with succinct education about each prescription medication. The RN evaluated this initial education using the teach-back method, having participants repeat given instructions. Following the implementation of the intervention, the RN administered an evaluation of patient medication knowledge using a data collection table, discussed in the methods section, upon each subsequent visit during the project.

Study

As participants demonstrated the ability to state the name, dose, schedule, and purpose of their prescription medications, the author answered question two: *How will change or improvement be known?* When considering this question the RN evaluated the success of the education in improving medication adherence and knowledge of medication regimens (The Deming Institute, 2018) based on comparing scores at baseline, one-month, and two-month intervals. Both medication knowledge and self-efficacy of medication management were evaluated in the final data analysis.

Act

Based on the analysis of project findings, the RN considered if the intervention should be adopted, adapted, or abandoned (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017). In terms of this project, this stage of the PDSA cycle identified recommendations for future projects and limitations of the project. Based on the project findings, the RN considered the project limitations and addressed question three: *What future changes can be made to result in improvement?* Repeating the four stages of the PDSA leads to continued improvement in the area of interest (The Deming Institute, 2018).

Nola Pender's Health Promotion Model

While the PDSA model provided an organizational process framework for the project, Nola Pender's Health Promotion Model (HPM) theoretically contributed a supportive structure for concepts and variables of interest within the project (McEwen & Wills, 2014). According to Pender, health is not the absence of disease; rather, it is a dynamic state of well-being for the individual (Current Nursing, 2011). The HPM encourages nurses to collaborate with patients to promote optimal health outcomes, thus

supporting the purpose of this project. Patients must be motivated to perform health-promoting behaviors, such as improving their knowledge about their medication regimens, to enhance their well-being (Polit & Beck, 2017). The focus on health promotion made Pender's theory useful in the primary care setting where patients often received preventative care. Application of the HPM to this project allowed for consideration of individual characteristics and experiences, behavior-specific cognitions and affect, and behavioral outcomes affecting health promotion among patients (McEwen & Wills, 2014).

Individual Characteristics and Experiences

Individual characteristics (e.g., age, gender, self-esteem, ethnicity, motivation, education level, perceived health status) and previous experiences influenced knowledge related to self-management of medications and medication adherence. Identifying baseline characteristics aided in the planning of the interventions for this project. Consideration of personal factors was important for developing a successful quality improvement project (Current Nursing, 2011).

Behavior-Specific Cognitions and Affect

The HPM conceptualizes thoughts (perceptions) as cognitions that affect changes in behavior related to health. *Perceived benefits of action* addressed the positive outcomes associated with a given health behavior. *Barriers to action* may have included actual or anticipated barriers to understanding a certain behavior. *Perceived self-efficacy* influenced anticipated barriers—these perceptions decrease as confidence increases in one's ability to perform a behavior. *Activity-related affect* is a concept that describes the patient's subjective feelings which occur prior to, during, and following change to a

health behavior (Current Nursing, 2011). *Interpersonal influences*, such as family, peers, healthcare providers, and norms as well as situational influences, such as perceptions of options available that directly or indirectly influence one's health behaviors (Current Nursing, 2011). These beliefs along with the individual characteristics of the individual may have directly affected the patient's level of commitment to a given plan.

Behavioral Outcomes

A patient's ability to commit to the plan of action based on his or her own preferences and competing demands may affect successful implementation of the health promotion behavior (Current Nursing, 2011). A patient's environment or their work or family commitments may compete with their desire and ability to perform the health behavior. For example, an older adult may find it a priority to care for an incapacitated spouse while placing a lower priority on his/her own health needs.

Consideration of these three key areas of the HPM allowed the RN to enhance a patient's capacity for self-care and self-efficacy of medication management through focused education aimed at health promotion (McEwen & Wills, 2014). Nurses tailor interventions and the plan of care to the individual's needs. In terms of this project, implementation of evidence-based activities directed at health promotion increased the likelihood of a patient improving their knowledge about their medication regimens. The HPM promoted a positive behavior change when the patient perceived such activities as health-enhancing (Polit & Beck, 2017). A conceptual representation of the HPM concisely presents the key characteristics of this model as it applied to this project (see Appendix B).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Appraising the literature is an integral step needed to gain knowledge regarding current evidence related to a planned practice change. The author reviewed the following databases: PubMed, Google Scholar, CINAHL, and the Cochrane Library. Search terms included medication adherence, medication knowledge, self-efficacy, older adults, medication self-management, polypharmacy, adverse medication events, and medication lists. The search was limited to English language journal articles published between 2013 and 2018. All articles were published in peer-reviewed journals of nursing, medicine, and pharmacology. A bibliography search from the selected articles was performed. Publications related to populations other than older adults were excluded. A discussion of recent literature related to medication adherence, medication self-management, and interventions to improve knowledge of medication regimens follows.

Medication Adherence

Medication adherence refers to one's ability to take medications as prescribed by their healthcare providers (Abada et al., 2017). Medication nonadherence is defined as neglecting to take medication as prescribed through missed doses, incorrect doses, or incorrect dose schedules (Sanders & Van Oss, 2013). Older adults are more likely than other patient populations to experience medication nonadherence due to the high number of prescription medications they take daily (Morabet et al., 2018; Mulhem et al., 2013; Naples et al., 2016) and the multiple providers involved in their care (Lee et al., 2014; Vandermause et al., 2016).

Most research studies examining medication adherence include discussions of the complexity of medication regimens and the related incidence of adverse drug events

(ADEs) (Appendix C, Table 1). ADEs are any negative physical, psychological, or functional sequelae from medication use (Abada et al., 2017; Mulhem et al., 2013; Wilson, Greer, & Weeks, 2014). ADEs are a primary cause of rehospitalization within 30 days of discharge (Morabet et al., 2018; Willson, Greer, & Weeks, 2014). Many ADEs are preventable and are the result of medication errors due to nonadherence (Morabet et al., 2018). Researchers have identified interventions to improve adherence and mitigate the potential for ADEs.

A recent Cochrane review examined 12 studies, evaluating interventions to increase medication adherence among older adults with greater than four prescription medications. The review concluded these patients benefitted most from face-to-face (F2F) interactions with healthcare providers as a way to increase medication adherence (Cooper et al., 2014). Other studies confirmed the Cochrane review results (Marek et al., 2013; Meranius & Hammar, 2016, Vandermause et al., 2016) and agree that F2F involvement by the primary care provider increases medication adherence (Abada et al., 2017; Elliott et al., 2016; Mulhem et al., 2013). Many of the interventions reported in these studies focus on approaches to facilitate older adult's ability to self-manage their medication regimen.

Self-Management of Medication Regimens

Self-management refers to one's ability to independently obtain medication, plan a schedule to take medications, and know when to contact medical professionals about reactions or missed doses (Hain, Tappen, Diaz, & Ouslander, 2012). Successful self-management decreases the incidence of ADEs (Win, Mullan, Howard, & Oinas-Kukkonen, 2017; Meranius & Hammar, 2016; Elliott et al., 2016). Patients who report an

ability to manage their medications also have higher levels of self-efficacy, or confidence (Risser, Jacobson, & Kripalani, 2007) which decreases the likelihood of medication errors. Older adults are also at a higher risk than other age groups to have difficulties managing their medications due to physical changes associated with aging. For example, it may be difficult for this population to read medication labels or open medication bottles (Elliott et al., 2015; Hain, Tappen, Diaz, & Ouslander, 2012; Meranius & Hammar, 2016). In addition, older adults receive their prescription medications from more than one setting, such as a local pharmacy as well as a mail-order pharmacy. Thus, they may receive conflicting instructions interfering with self-management and have issues coordinating refills from multiple settings. The literature identified several evidence-based interventions to improve older adults' knowledge regarding their medications in order to promote medication self-management and adherence (Cadogan et al., 2018; Conn et al., 2015; Kwint et al., 2013, Lee et al., 2014).

Interventions to Improve Knowledge about Medication Regimens

The choice of an intervention to improve knowledge about medication regimens should consider a patient's current functional and cognitive status, demographic data, past medication adherence, and current knowledge about their medication routine (Elliott et al., 2015; Hain et al., 2012). Interventions range from the provision of a simple medication list to the use of technological electronic medication dispensers. Among adults aged 65 and older, the use of technology to improve adherence is not consistently successful (Kwint et al., 2013; Meranius & Hammar, 2015). Electronic medication dispensers may be cumbersome and expensive. Many of these units require pre-filling of medication drawers and detailed programming, which contributes to confusion among

older adults and acts as a deterrent to self-management. Another limitation of electronic dispensers is the inability to load over-the-counter medications and medications taken on an “as needed” basis, such as prescription analgesics (Kwint et al, 2013).

Alternatively, the use of a combination of simple interventions over time has been shown to be most effective (Cadogan et al., 2018; Lam & Fresco, 2015; Conn et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2014). Older adults benefit from face-to-face (F2F) education regarding their personal medication regimen (Sollitto, 2017; Cadogan et al., 2018; Win et al., 2017). Personal interaction is especially important with older adults who require a quiet environment free from distraction during education due to visual and hearing changes associated with aging (Eldercare Workforce Alliance, 2018). Use of home medication lists/charts with F2F education and follow-up phone calls and/or office visits improve medication adherence among older adults (Conn et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2013).

Summary of Literature Review

Studies have investigated multiple modalities to improve the knowledge and self-efficacy of older adults regarding their medication regimens. Technological approaches to improving adherence were rarely accepted by the older adult population (Kwint et al., 2013; Marek et al., 2013; Win, Mullan, Howard, & Oinas-Kukkonen, 2017).

Based on current evidence, older adults benefit from personal attention when receiving education regarding their medication regimens. Clear instructions accompanied by a concise, accurate medication list is effective at improving medication adherence and knowledge in the primary care setting (Abada et al., 2017; Cadogan et al., 2018; Cooper et al., 2015; Marek et al., 2013 Vandermause et al., 2016). Some studies suggest interval

follow up phone calls and/or office visits to reinforce medication regimen information and improve medication adherence (Cadogan et al., 2018; Conn et al, 2015). Such findings from the literature review support the “Back to Basics” plan for this DNP project.

METHODS

The aim of this quality improvement (QI) project was to improve patient knowledge regarding medications and self-efficacy of medication management in a primary care setting by developing, implementing, and evaluating evidence-based activities that support self-management of medication regimens. QI projects intend to improve the processes of care among a given group in a particular setting (Polit & Beck, 2017). The design, sample, setting, ethical considerations, measures, procedures, and analysis plan for this project are presented in this chapter.

Design

This project was a quality improvement (QI) project; quality improvement activities are designed to improve practices or processes within a specific setting (Polit & Beck, 2017). QI projects use an accelerated process, such as the PDSA Model, to facilitate rapid change based on data that can transform patient care (The Deming Institute, 2018).

Sample

A convenience sample of 50 participants from the principle author's practice provided the patient sample for this project. Criteria for inclusion were: age 65 or older, taking four or more prescription medications, Mini-Cog score of 4-5, home dwelling, in possession of a phone, English-speaking, having the visual ability to read medication lists generated from electronic medical record, and being a current patient at the project setting described below. Although consideration for inclusion of patients with a Mini-Cog score below four was dependent upon the willingness of a full-time caregiver to be

educated and assist patient, none agreed to participate. The procedures section details further patient screening information.

Setting

The setting for the project was an Internal Medicine (IM) office in South Orange County, California. The office primarily serves a population of patients living in a retirement community located less than one mile from the office. The doctor provides care to 12-18 patients in the office on a typical day. The majority of patients are over 65 years. The IM office staff consists of a medical doctor (MD), a registered nurse (RN), and a medical assistant (MA). The RN was the principle author of this project. Along with the office staff, stakeholders included the patients, their families, and the staff of the Internal Medicine office, and other healthcare providers involved in the patient's care. The following section presents a procedural outline of the project.

Procedures

The management staff at the medical office approved this project. All data collection occurred at the IM office by the RN. The following steps outline the procedure followed for project completion:

- Obtained an IRB determination
- Presented the project to stakeholders—office staff, office managers
- Posted flyers in waiting room, exam rooms (Appendix D)
- Recruited participants
 - Participants interested in project contacted the RN

- Participants provided preliminary permission for electronic medical record (EMR) screening for age and number of medications (See Script, Appendix E; EMR tool, Appendix F)
- Participants were screened with cognitive tool for eligibility (Appendix G)
- Participants meeting project inclusion criteria received a project description
 - Participants signed a consent and received a copy of the consent (Appendix H)
 - Participant's signed consent was stored in separate folder; surveys only used a tracking number
 - RN confirmed phone number with patient and verified number in EMR
- RN administered the Self-Efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use Scale (SEAMS) (Appendix I) and Medication Knowledge Assessment Tool (MKAT) (Appendix J)
 - RN read the survey questions aloud and recorded participant's responses
- Participants had current medications reconciled with RN in EMR
 - Current medication list generated (Appendix K)
- Participants received 20 minutes of education regarding medication properties
 - Name
 - Dose
 - Schedule
 - Purpose

- Importance of having current medication list
- Importance of calling RN with any medication changes
- Participants “teach-back” the education to RN and asked questions
- Participants were contacted with phone call by RN within 2 days to reinforce education, answer questions
- SEAMS and MKAT tools were re-administered at 1- and 2-month intervals following same procedure, including follow-up phone call within 2 days
 - Follow-up F2F education took place if medications had changed or if reinforcement of information needed
 - Participants were offered option of completing tools in office or by phone
- Hard copies of surveys were kept in a locked drawer in a locked office
- Data from the demographic/clinical survey and pre/post surveys were entered into an excel spread sheet on a password-protected computer for analysis

Measurement Tools

The Mini-Cog is a cognitive screening tool that includes two simple tasks: a three-item word recall exercise and a clock drawing exercise (Borson, Scanlan, Chen, & Ganguli, 2003). The three-item recall serves to assess memory and the clock drawing assesses executive function and distracts from the item recall. Scores range from 0-5, with scores of 3-5 indicating a low probability of cognitive impairment (Holsinger et al., 2012). A score of ≥ 4 is the cut off for patient inclusion with this project. This tool is effective for screening older adults in the primary care setting for cognitive impairments with a sensitivity of 76-99% and specificity of 89-93% with a 95% confidence interval (Doerflinger, 2007).

A multidisciplinary team of experts in health literacy and medication adherence developed the Self-efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use Scale (SEAMS) (Risser, Jacobson, & Kripalani, 2007). The SEAMS tool caters to participants with varying literacy skills. The tool consists of thirteen questions about medication adherence which participants rate using a Likert scale to indicate their level of confidence in terms of each question: 1 = not confident, 2 = somewhat confident, and 3 = very confident (Appendix I). Scores range from 13-39, with higher scores indicating higher levels of self-efficacy for medication adherence (Risser, Jacobson, & Kripalani, 2007). Analyses performed showed the SEAMS to be a reliable and valid tool among all literacy levels with an internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.89$) and criterion-related validity strongly correlated with medication adherence ($p = .0001$) for the self-efficacy scale (Risser, Jacobson, & Kripalani, 2007). Such a tool is low cost and easy to implement (Stirratt et al., 2015). A quick administration time and immediate scoring make this tool useful in the primary care setting.

A Medication Knowledge Assessment Tool (MKAT) was developed by the principle author (Appendix J) to assess patients' knowledge of medication name (generic or brand), dose (in mg, mcg, etc.), schedule, and purpose. Participants received one point for each correct answer and an additional point if they possess a current medication list at each office visit. Such a tool is a simple way of using numerical values to represent and measure attributes of a project (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). Three internists in the medical office reviewed the tool for face validity. No other valid tool to measure medication knowledge which met the project criteria and explicit aims was identified in the literature. The validity was further examined by comparing scores of the SEAMS with the MKAT

scores; high scores on the AE should correlate with low scores on the MKAT. The SEAMS and MKAT were the tools administered for data collection at baseline, 1-month post-education, and 2-months post-education. In the interest of time and consistency, the RN read the survey questions aloud and recorded the participant's responses.

“Back to Basics” Medication Education

The participants received standardized F2F education focused on their personal medication regimens and instructions about when to phone the IM office. Caregivers, family members, or spouses accompanying participants were encouraged to participate in the focused education to serve as an added support to the patient. Items for discussion included medication name, dose, schedule, and purpose as well as reinforcement of the importance of medication adherence. A current medication list including these four items provided participants with essential information regarding their medication regimen (Appendix K). Printing the medication lists on yellow paper and placing them in a page protector distinguished them from other handouts the participants may possess. Following one-on-one patient education, the RN provided encouragement for patient participants to call with any questions or concerns. Printed instructions to call the IM office if any specialists changed medications or if they had questions regarding their medications were on the back of the medication list. The RN called the patient 2 days following instruction to support patient education.

Data Analysis and Evaluation Plan

Once all data was collected and tabulated, changes of participants' aggregate scores for self-efficacy (SEAMS score) and knowledge (MKAT score) were examined at

baseline, one-month, and two-month follow up. In addition, item-level analysis was conducted to identify specific topics with improvements or decrement.

The data were entered on an excel spreadsheet and included:

- Coded demographic/clinical data from EMR and patient input
- Medication data (name, dose, schedule, purpose)
- SEAMS, MKAT item scores at baseline, one-month, two-months

The IBM SPSS Statistical software version 25 and Excel were used for data analysis. Expression of MKAT scores as percentages (number of correct items/total number of items) facilitated assessing change between baseline and 1 month and between one- and two-months. Measures of central tendency, as appropriate, were used to describe baseline/clinical characteristics of the sample. Results are shown using graphs and figures, as appropriate.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional Review Board (IRB) determination was procured from California State University, Long Beach. If a patient expressed interest in participating and met inclusion criteria, the RN met with them and then informed consent was obtained. The data that were collected from the EMR and from participants were coded to ensure privacy. The principle author kept the master list of patient names and codes in a locked drawer in a locked office until the data collection was completed. Following completion of data collection, the completed surveys and forms were kept in a locked file cabinet in the principle author's home and the consents remained in the locked cabinet at the principle author's office. Participants did not receive any incentive for participation in the project.

RESULTS: PROJECT MANUSCRIPT

A manuscript including the project results, recommendations, and limitations was created to be submitted to *Geriatric Nursing*, a peer-reviewed journal focusing on care for older adults across settings. Specific manuscript preparation guidelines provided by the journal were followed. *Geriatric Nursing* publishes original manuscripts about all aspects of aging and welcomes the submission of DNP projects. The submitted manuscript is located in Appendix L. Authors' guidelines provided by *Geriatric Nursing* are located at the following website: www.elsevier.com/journals/geriatric-nursing/0197-4572/guide-for-authors.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this evidence-based project was to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy among adults aged 65 and older in a primary care setting. Developing, implementing, and evaluating evidence-based activities to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy were specific aims of this project. Most studies in the literature focused on either medication knowledge or self-efficacy but did not address the importance of addressing both topics among one sample (Elliott et al., 2016; Marek et al., 2013; Vandermause et al., 2016).

Older adults value their independence. The simple act of self-managing their medication regimens allows them to gain higher levels of self-efficacy. Medication self-efficacy decreases errors (Abada et al., 2017) and facilitates the ability to lead independent lives. The SEAMS tool was a reliable assessment tool to gauge self-efficacy for appropriate medication use as demonstrated by strong to moderate internal consistency coefficients of .82, .81, and .75 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively.

Surprisingly, most participants had high levels of self-efficacy for medication management as indicated by their SEAMS scores at baseline, one-month, and two-months. The following items, in order, on the SEAMS tool showed the greatest improvement over time: item 11 (*When you are not sure how to take the medication*), item 12 (*When you are not sure what time of day to take your medication*), and item 1 (*When you get a refill of your old medications and some of the pills look different*). With standardized education, self-efficacy regarding these areas increased the most among the items. SEAMS tool items with the lowest levels of improvement over time were: item 6

(*When you have a busy day planned*) and item 8 (*When no one reminds you to take the medications*). These areas may have shown little improvement because participants' reported high levels of self-efficacy at baseline and a suspected ceiling effect. Since the majority of participants rated these items higher at baseline, there was little likelihood of improvement.

The MKAT tool was used to assess participants' ability to recall their medication names, doses, schedules, and purposes and to verify if a current medication list was in the participants' possession. Though most participants rated their self-efficacy of medication management high at baseline, many had limited knowledge of their medications. In fact, the majority of participants did not know their correct medication doses. Participants' knowledge of medication doses improved slightly after receiving education about the variety of doses associated with their particular medications. For example, many participants taking atorvastatin were not aware the medication was available in 10mg, 20mg, 40mg, and 80mg doses. In hindsight, it would be beneficial if the data from the MKAT were itemized to examine where the participants' primary weaknesses were in terms of their medication regimens. Also, MKAT scores may have shown only a mild increase due to participants relying on their medication lists rather than learning about their medications.

There was gradual improvement noted when comparing the SEAMS and MKAT scores at baseline, one-month, and two-month intervals. Gradual changes can be seen more frequently among older adults and are particularly characteristic of health behavior changes. Such changes may be more significant if the project took place over a longer length of time. A longer project period may have been more conducive to changing

health behavior especially when considering the older adult population and their unique needs. Though the mean SEAMS scores showed only slight improvement of 2.73, 2.83, and 2.85 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively, these differences were statistically significant ($p = .000$).

With the mean number of medications being 8, the decreased ability to memorize one's medication regimen is understandable. Thus, possessing a current medication list is of utmost importance to older adults who may not be able to recall every detail of their medication regimen. At baseline, 34% of participants carried a medication list. After receiving education and follow up phone calls, the percentage increased to 68% and 88% (one- and two-months, respectively). Thus, there was a 158% increase from baseline to two-months. The increase was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 12.12, p = .000$).

Implications for Practice

The project findings may be replicable in other care settings. If older adults were able to gain medication knowledge and improve their levels of medication self-efficacy in the primary care setting, they may also benefit from similar approaches in hospital settings or specialists' offices. Other patient populations could receive similar interventions with the same results, if not better. Regardless of age or healthcare setting, all patients could benefit from standardized education regarding their specific medications. Medication errors could decrease and levels of self-efficacy increase. The simple act of providing each patient with a current medication list and encouraging them to bring it to each healthcare visit would reduce adverse drug events and raise levels of patient safety. It must be noted, however, that initial data collection and education at baseline were time consuming and required longer visits with the patients initially.

Limitations

The small sample size ($n = 50$) and the convenience sample used for this project limit generalizability to other primary care settings. In addition, time constraints further limited recruitment and desired length of follow up (e.g. 6 months). The use of self-report, especially when the principle author read questions aloud and recorded participant responses, could have lead participants to respond favorably (social desirability).

Conclusion

This project showed face-to-face education and provision of an accurate medication list increases medication self-efficacy and knowledge regarding medication regimens in primary care settings. While most studies support either medication adherence or medication knowledge, this project linked the two concepts. Further projects are needed to investigate different age groups and care settings to ascertain if these findings could translate to different settings and samples. While different teaching strategies may be more beneficial with other age groups and settings, older adults in the primary care setting responded positively to the “back to basics” approach that is based on face-to-face, standardized teaching.

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APPENDIX A

THE PLAN-DO-STUDY-ACT MODEL/CYCLE

Note. Adapted from The Deming Institute, 2018.

APPENDIX B

NOLA PENDER'S HEALTH PROMOTION MODEL

Note. Adapted from Current Nursing, 2011.

APPENDIX C
TABLES OF SUPPORTING EVIDENCE

Table 1

Medication Adherence in Older Adults

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
(Abada et al., 2017) To determine relationship between med regimen complexity and level of adherence	Cross-sectional analysis: 2 ^o analysis of data from 1 ^o intervention to ↑ med adherence in community-dwelling older adults 12-month study; dates not stated Variables: age, race/ethnicity, gender, living situation, marital status, education, income	N = 31 IC: ≥ 65 y/o, English or Spanish speaking, community-dwelling, APS-substantiated self-neglect, taking meds for chronic disease, capable of providing informed consent, w/i 1-h driving distance to Houston, TX	Data collected in-person, in-home by RN and trained associate Multiple assessment tools applied: MMAS, MRCI, MMSE, TMT, CLOX-I, Geriatric Depression Scale Statistical software for data analysis: SAS, STATA	64.5% female, mean age 74.5 ↑ complexity of med regimen leads to ↓ med adherence	Med regimen complexity significantly associated with adherence levels in older adults who self-neglect; complexity alone is a barrier to adherence Clinicians must review meds, assess complexity of regimens, make changes to facilitate adherence Limitations: original data from pilot study using pre- and post-test design w/o control group; sample not randomly chosen
(Cooper et al., 2015)	Cochrane systematic review	12 articles: 8 RCTs, 2 cluster RCTs, 2	MeSH terms: Polypharmacy, MAI, inappropriate meds,	Interventions included pharmacy involvement,	Med adherence enhanced by face-to-face interaction; too few

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
Summary of Cochrane review re: improving appropriate med use among older adults with multiple meds (≥ 4)	IV: interventions to improve polypharmacy DV: change in preponderance of rightful polypharmacy and hospital admissions, med related problems, med adherence Studies from inception of data bases to November 2013	controlled before/after studies IC: interventions targeting people ≥ 65 y/o, > 1 medical condition, ≥ 4 meds; no language restrictions EC: studies re: short-term polypharmacy Setting: across all healthcare settings—home, hospital, SNFs	inappropriate rxs, over-rx, under-rx, number rx, med errors, med interactions, aged, geriatric, vulnerable elders, adverse drug rxn... Compared summated MAI scores, change in MAI scores	patient education, & provider education Selected interventions \downarrow inappropriate rx'ing No clinically significant improvements with \downarrow # of meds	studies to generalize results; too wide variety/number of interventions addressed; poor quality of studies
(Mulhem et al., 2013) To evaluate med adherence rates of older adults after hospital d/c	Descriptive Design using mixed methods 2009-- 2010	N = 46 IC: ≥ 65 y/o, d/c from Beaumont Hospital, Troy, MI, w/i 24-48 hours to home setting EC: d/c to facility other than home, documented dementia dx Setting: suburban SE MI	Family medicine residents provided home med list, instruction upon d/c; used author-generated check list to collect data at home visits and from EMR Home visits by family medicine residents w/i 24-48 hrs, compared d/c med list with what pts taking since d/c	Mean age 76, 54.4% female, average # meds: 9.98 Only 6.5% adhered completely; 78.2% took at least 1 additional med not on list; 43.4% omitted at least 1 med; 43.4% took wrong dose at least once; 41.3% varied ordered frequency	Majority of subjects nonadherent w/i 24-48 hours from d/c; strong positive association between \uparrow # meds and \downarrow med adherence Limitations: inadequate addressing of OTC med use on d/c lists, lack of pharmacy involvement
(Unni, Shiyabola, & Farris, 2016)	Longitudinal descriptive study 2005-- 2007	N = 436	Internet-based survey, administered by confidential panel	Mean age 72.54, 55% female	Neither adherence nor beliefs in medicines among older adults changed over time

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
To assess changes in med adherence and beliefs in meds over time among older adults	Variables: age, gender, education, self-reported health, # daily meds	IC: ≥ 65 , at least 1 med, enrolled in online survey panel	Adherence measured by MMAS-4 item scale Beliefs measured by BMQ	Baseline med adherence score 0.58, follow-up score 0.59—no significant change SS: those with initial \downarrow adherence had \uparrow adherence over time Overall no change in beliefs SS: those initially non-adherent had \uparrow concern beliefs at baseline and follow-up	Baseline adherence and concern beliefs play significant role in change in adherence over time Limitations: baseline adherence of sample high, beliefs addressed were general, not med-type specific, convenience sample, specific chronic diseases not isolated/addressed
(Willson, Greer, & Weeks, 2014) To determine relationship between med regimen complexity, med adherence, and hospital admission rate for ADEs	Retrospective parallel-group case-control study 2009--2010 Variables: age, sex, LOS, race, admission source, admission dx code, d/c disposition, admission and d/c med list	N = 92 re-visit, 228 control Re-visit group: had ADE rehospitalization; Control group did not IC for re-visit: all pts with any d/c dx rehospitalized w/I 30 days of d/c for ADE Control: matched by sex, age, initial d/c dx Setting: 4 urban, acute care hospitals	Data extraction from EMR Complexity of med lists measured by MRCI	41% female re-visit, 42% female control; age 50.29 re-visit, 49.39 control # meds of re-visit group significantly greater than control ($P < .001$) \uparrow complexity of med regimen leads to \uparrow occurrence of ADE rehospitalization	Med regimen complexity important to assess to plan d/c interventions to \downarrow risk of readmission Limitations: severity of diseases not considered, admission med lists based on pt recall, lack of established threshold for sensitivity and specificity of MRCI

Note: ADE: Adverse Drug Event; APS: Adult Protective Services; BMQ: Beliefs About Medicines Questionnaire; CLOX-I: Clock-Drawing Task; D/C: Discharge; Demo: Demographic; DV: Dependent Variable; Dx: Diagnosis; EC: Exclusion Criteria; EMR: Electronic Medical Record; IC: Inclusion Criteria; IV: Independent Variable; LOS: Length of Stay; MAI = Medication Appropriateness Index ; Med: Medication; MeSH = Medical Subject Headings; MI: Michigan; MMAS: Morisky Medication Adherence Scale; MMSE: Mini-Mental State Examination; MRCI: Medication Regimen Complexity, Index; N: Sample Size; OTC: Over-The-Counter; Pt: Patient; RCT: Randomized Controlled Trials; RN: Registered Nurse; Rx: Prescription; Rxn: Reaction; SE: Southeast; SNF: Skilled Nursing Facility; SS: Statistically Significant; TMT: Trail Making Test; TX: Texas; W/I: Within; W/O: Without; Y/O: Years Old; ↓: Decreased ; ≥: Greater or Equal To; ↑: Increased; #: Number; 1^o: Primary; 2^o: Secondary

Table 2

Medication Self-Management Among Older Adults: Quantitative Studies

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
(Elliott, Lee, Beanland, Vakil, & Goeman, 2016) To describe characteristics of older people in community setting referred to CNS for med mgmt education, med errors, and AMEs	Retrospective observational study 2012-2013 Variables: demographics, referral source, current med problems, meds, med aids, frequency of nurse visits, med errors, AMEs	N = 100, random sample IC: aged ≥ 50 , referred for med support Setting: two nonprofit CNS in Melbourne, Australia	Author-generated form Measures: demo data; referral source; current med problems; meds; med aids; nurse visit frequency, support provided; medication authorizations; med errors; AMEs; interdisciplinary teamwork	Median age 80, 60% female, median # meds 5, 81% referred for med mgmt only, 56% in home setting Few had current med chart, only 15 had upon d/c; most only had partial med lists; 48% had high risk meds; little evidence of interdisciplinary teamwork 39.1% had med-related hospitalizations during study; 64% with preventable AMEs	Interdisciplinary collaboration and med reconciliation improves med safety, decreases med errors, and AMEs; important to have current med list on d/c Authors suggest international findings similar to this study Limitations: only one metropolitan area included, may affect generalizability; retrospective collection affects interpretation
(Gamble et al., 2014) To describe changes in patterns of med use among older patients	Population-based, prospective study From 2000-2002	N = 2105 IC: ≥ 65 y/o, hospitalized with CAP, alive w/i 1 yr after hospitalization, at least 5 meds (authors'	Author generated forms for use in MR # of meds at baseline then 90-day intervals for 1 yr after CAP	Mean age 78 Mean # of meds at baseline: 4.5 (SD 2.8) with 45% 5 or more	Greatest \uparrow in meds noted w/i 90-days after d/c for CAP pts; over 1 yr, most continued on more meds

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
before and 1 yr after hospitalization for CAP		definition of polypharmacy) EC: dx of TB or CF, immunocompromised, pregnant Setting: seven EDs in Edmonton, Alberta, Canada	Conducted by trained research nurses	80% started 1 new med during yr Polypharmacy ↑ from 45% to 74%	80% started and 74% stopped at least 1 med during yr Conclusion: post-d/c phase requires med review to ↓ med errors, optimize correct med use; transition of care crucial Limitations: only CAP pts, pre-hospital meds based on pt self-report; OTC meds not addressed; focus on abx; medication regimen complexity not addressed
(Marek et al., 2013) To compare effect of nurse coordination with or without med dispensing tools is when helping older adults with med self-mgmt	RCT 3 arms— control group, one group with RN & manual med-minder, one group with RN & electronic med dispenser Study over 12-month period; dates not provided	N = 125 in control group—no RN or med N = 137 in group with RN & manual med-minder N = 152 in group with RN & electronic med dispenser IC: ≥ 60 y/o, Medicare pt, score of 1 or more on Outcome and Assessment Information Set, able to follow directions; telephone access	All groups had baseline pharmacy screens Measurement tools assessed at baseline, 3, 6, 9, and 12 months: Geriatric Depression Scale, MMSE, Physical Performance Test, SF-36 Physical Component Summary, Mental Component Summary Visits q 2 wks or after ER/hospital visits; meds reinforced, med dispensers filled by RN; dispensers checked for missed doses	Pts with RN & manual med-minder had better health outcomes than control group and group with RN & electronic med dispenser Use of technology did not improve outcomes—time with RN most important factor	Conclusion: home-based RN coordination with use of manual med-minder most effective at improved med mgmt; “checking in” with pt q 2 wks important for success; technology not always answer Limitations: attrition d/t appearance (large) of electronic med dispenser and need for hospitalizations > 2 months

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
		EC: terminal dx/hospice pt; use of other type med device Setting: pt's own home; US			

Note: Abx: Antibiotics; AME: Adverse Medication Event; CAP: Community-Acquired Pneumonia; CF: Cystic Fibrosis; CNS: Community Nursing Services; D/C: Discharge; Demo: Demographic; DRUGS: Drug Regimen Unassisted Grading Scale; Dx: Diagnosis; EC: Exclusion Criteria; ED: Emergency Department; ER: Emergency Room; F/U: Follow-up; IC: Inclusion Criteria; ID: Identification; Med: Medication; Mgmt: Management; MMSE: Mini-Mental State Examination; MR: Medical Record; N: Sample Size; OTC: Over-The-Counter; Pt: Patient; Q: Every; RCT: Randomized Controlled Trial; RN: Registered Nurse; SD: Standard Deviation; TB: Tuberculosis; US: United States; W/I: Within; Wks: Weeks; Y/O: Years Old; Yr: Year; ↓: Decrease; = : Equal; >: Greater Than; ≥: Greater Or Equal To; ↑: Increase; #: Number.

Table 3

Medication Self-Management among Older Adults: Qualitative Studies

Purpose	Design/Philosophy/Key Phenomenon	Sample/Setting/Data Collection	Results	Conclusions, Limitations
(Meranius & Hammar, 2016) To discover interventions health care workers provide to support med self-mgmt among older adults	Hermeneutic approach	N = 20 IC: ≥ 75 ; living at home; hospitalized 3 or more times in past 12 months Setting: medium-sized urban town in Sweden Unstructured interviews; results analyzed by Gadamer's hermeneutic approach	11 men, 9 women aged 76-83 Three levels: 1 st : Pt's found lack of involvement from health care, felt abandoned re: self-care needs 2 nd : Healthcare organization obstacle to self-medication mgmt 3 rd : Repairing "parts" without enabling health experience	Healthcare system a hindrance to pt's medication self-management, focuses primarily on interaction with MD MDs avoid responsibility of encouraging, addressing med self-mgmt Encourage nurse participation with health-centered approach in pt education to promote self-care, self-mgmt
(Vandermause et al., 2016) Twofold purpose: a) identify med-taking behaviors of older adults with MCMCs b) interpret meaning of med taking among this population	Multimethod qualitative design; post-positivist and phenomenological approaches	N = 30 IC: ≥ 60 ; at least 3 chronic medical dxs; at least 5 meds; a new med rx; home-dwelling; English-speaking; ability to participate in 120 minute interviews Setting: in pt's own homes	Specifics: age 69 ± 6.9 ; 48% female; 92% Caucasian; #MCMCs 8.8 ± 4.2 ; #meds 11.9 ± 4.4 ; most common dx HTN Issues r/t rx itself: transportation issues, pharmacy out of pills; insurance noncoverage	Patients need more conversation with providers when adding new med to regimen; meds affect pt self-worth, sense of health/well-being Tools needed for pts to engage providers, manage care, especially re: med regimen

Purpose	Design/Philosophy/Key Phenomenon	Sample/Setting/Data Collection	Results	Conclusions, Limitations
		In-depth hermeneutic interviews (2 with 15 subjects), self-assessment electronic diaries recorded daily for all 30 subjects Hermeneutic analysis, EMA, content analysis	Issues r/t med taking process: timing issues; concern with SEs; undifferentiated worry “Preserving self” themes: illness effects on identity, function, social life; engaging with providers to address health, lifestyles	Limitations: electronic journaling may influence pts’ usual med taking; sample limited geographically; small sample

Note. Dx = Diagnosis; EMA = Ecological Momentary Assessment; GP = General Practitioner; HTN = Hypertension; IC: Inclusion Criteria; MCMC = Multiple Chronic Medical Conditions; MD = Medical Doctor/Physician; Med = Medication; Mgmt = Management; N: Sample Size; Pt = Patient; R/T = Related To; Rx = Prescription; SE = Side Effects; Y/O = Years Old; \geq : Greater Or Equal To; # = Number; \pm = Plus/Minus.

Table 4

Interventions to Improve Knowledge of Medication Regimens

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
(Cadogan et al., 2018) To assess two-part intervention: video education for GPs re: appropriate rx'ing and med review consultations with pts to review meds	Multiphase mixed methods feasibility study (Article outlines 2 nd phase of project—initial phase qualitative study) IVs: Video for GPs; med consult for pts DV: appropriate rx'ing for GPs; positive response to focused care	N = 4 GPs in 2 practice settings; 10 pts—5 from each setting IC: ≥ 65 y/o, not cognitively impaired, community resident, able to attend med consult on specified date EC: SNF residents Setting: 2 GP offices in UK	Video viewed by GPs before med consults with pts One-on-one med consults with GP Structured questionnaires with few open-ended questions after consults Convenience sampling for GPs; GPs chose pts based on IC Clinical data extracted from MR: demos, STOPP, START, MAI, MRCI data	GPs: 3 female, 3 in one setting, 1 in other Pts: 6 female, 5 per setting, mean age 73.5, mean # meds 6 GPs agreed intervention improved rx'ing appropriateness Both GPs and Pts gave positive feedback re: med consults Interventions found to be useable and acceptable/feasible	Feasibility study found intervention of video for GPs and med consults with pts improved rx'ing appropriateness for older pts Findings to help design future RCT Limitations: short study with f/u in 1 month, difficulty applying BCT coding to study; limited pt sample
(Conn et al., 2015) Comprehensive analysis of studies aimed to ↑ med adherence in pt with HTN	Systematic review with meta-analysis Dates of studies: 1973-2013	N = 101 studies IC: any study testing interventions to ↑ med adherence in pts with HTN as outcome measure	MeSH terms: pt compliance, med adherence, medications, regimens, drugs, promote, improve...	88 published articles, 10 dissertations, 2 conference presentations, 1 unpublished report Interventions with multiple components	Most successful interventions: linking behavior to daily habits, providing feedback to pt, motivational interviewing

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
			Multiple databases, 19 grant databases & clinical trial registries, journal hand searches, 48 conference abstracts, bibliography searches	delivered over many days most successful	Limitations: missed studies despite extensive search, heterogeneous samples, coding differences, studies lacking med info, use of self-report
(Kwint et al., 2013) To compare med adherence and knowledge among older adults using MDD vs. no MDD	Cross-sectional study 2010—2012 IV: MDD with nursing education DV: Increased medication adherence	N = 119 MDD users, 96 non-users, groups matched on age, gender IC: ≥65 y/o, at least 5 meds, home-dwelling or in residential care EC: Pts in SNFs Setting: 8 communities in the Netherlands	Med adherence assessed with MARS, knowledge by direct questioning, cognitive function by MMSE Med lists from community pharmacy, interviews by pharmacist	MDD users: mean age 80, 74% female, mean # meds 9.7 Non-users: mean age 81, 63% female, mean # meds 10 MDD users more adherent than non-users (P<0.001) Non-users had greater med knowledge than MDD users (P<0.001)	MDD promotes ↑ med adherence but ↓ knowledge of meds compared to no MDD; MDD users had lower MMSE scores Limitations: use of self-report, no standard med adherence tool, MDD system pre-filled so not able to assess med refill dates, not all meds applicable for MDD use, cross-sectional study unable to find causal relationship
(Lee et al., 2014) To assess pts' personal med lists for completeness as compared to clinic med lists	Cross-sectional study 2010—2010	N = 82 IC: ≥18 y/o, scheduled for elective, non-cardiac surgery, anticipated LOS > 1 day, had 2 or more cardiac risk factors and hx of CAD	Pt personal med lists copied at preop visit Pts interviewed re: med hx by NP who constructed clinic med list	Mean age: 65, 43% female, mean # meds on personal lists 10 56% personal med lists incomplete, missing: med route (96%), indication (90%), schedule (79%), dose	Complete, accurate med lists crucial to ↓ med errors, ↑ appropriate med use Most pts unable to recall meds or provide current list

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions/Limitations
		EC: noncommunicative or non-English-speaking	NP also gathered data from pharmacy records, GP office records, other MRs	(49%), frequency (38%)	Interventions to encourage accurate med lists needed
		Setting: academic hospital preop clinic in San Francisco	Differences analyzed with Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis and multivariate logistic regression		Limitations: only preop pts, may not be generalizable to other pts, pt med list requested—may be less accurate w/o prompting

Note: BCT: Behavior Change Technique; CAD: Coronary Artery Disease; Demo: Demographics; DP: Dependent Variable; EC: Exclusion Criteria; F/U: Follow Up; GP: General Practitioner; HTN: Hypertension; Hx: History; IC: Inclusion Criteria; IV: Independent Variable; LOS: Length of Stay; MAI: Medication Appropriateness Index; MARS: Medication Adherence Reporting Scale; MDD: Multidose Drug Dispenser; MeSH = Medical Subject Headings; MMSE: Mini-Mental State Examination; MR: Medical Record; MRCI: Medication Regimen Complexity Index; N: Sample Size; NP: Nurse Practitioner; Preop: Preoperative; START: Screening Tool to Alert Doctors to Right Treatment; STOPP: Screening Tool of Older People's Potentially Inappropriate Prescriptions; Pt: Patient; Rx: Prescribe/Prescription; RCT: Randomized Controlled Trial; SNF: Skilled Nursing Facility; UK: United Kingdom; Vs: Versus; W/O: Without; Y/O: Years Old; ↓: Decrease; >: Greater Than; ≥: Greater Than or Equal To; ↑: Increase; <: Less Than; #: Number.

APPENDIX D

FLYER FOR SAMPLE RECRUITMENT

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE
STUDENT SEEKING PROJECT
PARTICIPANTS

- ❖ Aged 65 and older

- ❖ Take 4 or more prescription medications

- ❖ Have interest in receiving one-on-one education about your medications

***Please contact Joelle @ 949- [REDACTED] for further information

APPENDIX E

SCRIPT FOR INCLUSION CRITERIA SCREENING

Author to Potential Participant: Thank you for your interest in my project. May I have your permission to verify your age and number of medications in your electronic medical record? In order to see if you are eligible to participate in my project, I need to conduct a quick memory test. After the test, I will explain the project in more detail, answer your questions, and have you sign consent to participate. You will be able to voluntarily terminate your involvement with the project at any time. I will be administering two surveys to give me information about your medication adherence and knowledge about your medications. These surveys will be administered again in 1 month and 2 months with the option of completing them in the office or by phone—whichever is more convenient for you. Do you have any questions for me?

APPENDIX F**ELECTRONIC MEDICAL RECORD (EMR) DATA EXTRACTION TOOL**

Demographic	From Patient	Verified EMR
Name:		
Age:		
Number of meds:		
Marital status:		
Possesses phone:		
Phone number:		
Able to read sample med list:		N/A

APPENDIX G

MINI-COGNITIVE ASSESSMENT TOOL

Mini-Cog

Instructions for Administration & Scoring

ID: _____ Date: _____

Step 1: Three Word Registration

Look directly at person and say, "Please listen carefully. I am going to say three words that I want you to repeat back to me now and try to remember. The words are [select a list of words from the versions below]. Please say them for me now." If the person is unable to repeat the words after three attempts, move on to Step 2 (clock drawing).

The following and other word lists have been used in one or more clinical studies.^{1,2} For repeated administrations, use of an alternative word list is recommended.

Version 1	Version 2	Version 3	Version 4	Version 5	Version 6
Banana	Leader	Village	River	Captain	Daughter
Sunrise	Season	Kitchen	Nation	Garden	Heaven
Chair	Table	Baby	Finger	Picture	Mountain

Step 2: Clock Drawing

Say, "Next, I want you to draw a clock for me. First, put in all of the numbers where they go." When that is completed, say, "Now, set the hands to 10 past 11."

Use preprinted circle (see next page) for this exercise. Repeat instructions as needed as this is not a memory test. Move to Step 3 if the clock is not complete within three minutes.

Step 3: Three Word Recall

Ask the person to recall the three words you stated in Step 1. Say, "What were the three words I asked you to remember?" Record the word list version number and the person's answers below.

Word List Version: _____ Person's Answers: _____

Scoring

Word Recall: _____ (0-3 points)	1 point for each word spontaneously recalled without cueing.
Clock Draw: _____ (0 or 2 points)	Normal clock = 2 points. A normal clock has all numbers placed in the correct sequence and approximately correct position (e.g., 12, 3, 6 and 9 are in anchor positions) with no missing or duplicate numbers. Hands are pointing to the 11 and 2 (11:10). Hand length is not scored. Inability or refusal to draw a clock (abnormal) = 0 points.
Total Score: _____ (0-5 points)	Total score = Word Recall score + Clock Draw score. A cut point of <3 on the Mini-Cog [®] has been validated for dementia screening, but many individuals with clinically meaningful cognitive impairment will score higher. When greater sensitivity is desired, a cut point of <4 is recommended as it may indicate a need for further evaluation of cognitive status.

Clock Drawing

ID: _____ Date: _____

Note. Adapted from Doerflinger, 2007. Permission received from S. Borson 3/7/19.

APPENDIX H
INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Notice of Informed Consent

Project Title: Back to Basics: Improving Patients' Knowledge and Attitudes about Medication Regimens in the Primary Care Setting

Investigator: Joelle Otteson, MSN, RN

Project Contact: 949-770-7691

California State University, Long Beach (CSULB)

Office of Research and Sponsored Programs, CSULB: 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840

You are being asked to participate in a Doctorate of Nursing Practice Project. The purpose of this study is to improve knowledge and attitudes regarding patients' medication regimens in the primary care setting by providing individual education. If you decide to participate you will be asked to sit with RN for 20 minutes to receive education, and answer questions on two brief surveys today, in one month, and in two months which are all for research purposes. The total time of your participation is expected to last approximately 60 minutes over the next two months. The risks to participating in this study include personal information being identified. The investigator will make every attempt to reduce these risks by providing a specific code number to each participant and keeping the master list in a locked drawer in a locked office. You may directly benefit from participating in this study by being more actively involved in learning about your medications. However, the results of this study may benefit all age groups treated in the primary care setting.

Any information collected from you in this study will be stored in a secure location and will not be shared with anyone who does not have appreciated provisions to access the information.

You may contact the Office of Research and Sponsored Programs at ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu, or by calling (562) 985-8147, if you have questions about your rights as a research participant.

Signing this document means that all information about the study has been explained to you orally, the investigator has answered any questions you have about the study and that you voluntarily agree to participate.

Name of Subject (Printed)

Subject Signature

Date

APPENDIX I

SELF-EFFICACY FOR APPROPRIATE MEDICATION USE SCALE (SEAMS)

How confident are you that you can take your medications correctly:

	Not at all confident	Somewhat confident	Very confident
1. When you get a refill of your old medications and some of the pills look different than usual?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. When a doctor changes your medications?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. When you take several different medications in each day?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. When you take medications more than once a day?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. When you are away from home?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. When you have a busy day planned?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. When they cause some side effects?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. When no one reminds you to take the medications?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. When the schedule to take the medications is not convenient?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. When your normal routine gets messed up?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. When you are not sure how to take the medication?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12. When you are not sure what time of day to take your medication?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13. When you are feeling sick (like having a cold or the flu)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Note. Adapted from Risser, Jacobson, & Kripalani, 2007. Permission received from J. Corwin 9/24/18.

APPENDIX J

MEDICATION KNOWLEDGE ASSESSMENT TOOL (MKAT)

Patient Code:

Medication	Name	Dose	Schedule	Purpose	Med List?	Total
A						/ 5
B					N/A	/ 4
C					N/A	/ 4
D					N/A	/ 4
Et cetera					N/A	/ 4

1 point for each correct name, dose, schedule, purpose for each medication (Possible 4/4)

1 point for bringing medication list (Med List) to each assessment (Possible 1/1)

Total will vary based on number of medications; expressed as a percentage

APPENDIX K

SAMPLE MEDICATION LIST

Patient: A Test
 Date of Birth: 12/30/1955
 Date: 04/16/2018 11:45 AM
 Present for: Office Visit

Active Medications:

Brand Name	Generic Name	Dose	Start Date	Instructions	Problem
OMEPRAZOLE	OMEPRAZOLE	20 mg		take 1 capsule by oral route every day 30 minutes to 1 hour before a meal	(K21.9) Gastro-esophageal reflux disease without esophagitis
DIGOXIN	DIGOXIN	125 mcg	04/16/2018	take 1 (125MCG) by oral route every day	(I49.9) Cardiac arrhythmia, unspecified
METOPROLOL SUCCINATE	METOPROLOL SUCCINATE	25 mg	04/16/2018	take 1 Tablet by oral route every day	(I10) Essential, (primary) hypertension
FUROSEMIDE	FUROSEMIDE	20 mg	04/16/2018	take 1 Tablet by oral route every day	(I10) Essential, (primary) hypertension

Instructions (on back of medication list)

Call office when:

- Any other doctor changes any medication(s)
- You have visited the Emergency Room/Hospital and have had medication changes or questions
- You have any questions regarding your medication names, doses, schedules, or reasons for taking medications

APPENDIX L**MANUSCRIPT TO BE SUBMITTED TO *GERIATRIC NURSING*****Back to basics: Improving patients' knowledge and self-efficacy of medication management in a primary care setting**

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Abstract

Adverse drug events (ADEs) result in 700,000 emergency department (ED) visits annually and are often the result of medication nonadherence. The majority of older adults take at least five medications. Standardized education regarding medications decreases detrimental medication errors. This quality improvement project improved knowledge and self-efficacy regarding medication regimens among adults aged 65 and older in a primary care setting. Standardized, evidence-based, patient education was implemented with 50 participants. Participants' self-efficacy and knowledge regarding their medications were evaluated at baseline, one-month, and two-month intervals and showed improvement at one- and two-months ($p = 0.05$ and 0.024 respectively). The

standardized educational approach along with providing a current medication list sustained a mean increase of 11% in medication knowledge at two-month follow up. The highest improvement was noticed in the rate of participants possessing a list of their current medications at clinic visits, which increased by 158%.

Keywords: older adults, self-efficacy, medication regimens, knowledge

Introduction

Adverse drug events (ADEs) result in 700,000 emergency department (ED) visits annually² and are often the result of medication nonadherence¹⁶. Older adults are twice as likely as other age groups to experience an ADE leading to an ED visit. In fact, this population is seven times more likely than other age groups to require hospitalization following such an event⁶. ADEs can occur due to medication omission, overuse, or misuse⁶. The older adult population is of special interest because this population is projected to double by 2030¹¹.

The majority of older adults take at least five prescription medications¹⁵ making their medication regimens more complicated than those of other patient populations. Another issue contributing to medication nonadherence among older adults is their lack of knowledge and casual attitudes regarding their medication regimens¹⁷. Often, patients lack the awareness of which medications are a part of their current medication regimen leading to either over or under use of prescription medications. Possessing accurate medication lists is key to assist older adults manage medications successfully.

Many medication errors are avoidable with the implementation of simple interventions such as the use of a medication administration chart¹². A medication chart provides a clear list of medication names, doses, schedules, and purposes⁶. Encouraging

patients to self-manage their medication regimens will promote and support health self-efficacy among this growing population and will improve outcomes¹⁷.

Studies have investigated several approaches to improve the knowledge and attitudes of older adults regarding their medication regimens. Technological approaches to improving adherence and decrease medication errors were rarely accepted by the older adult population^{15,17,23}. The practicality and cost-effectiveness of highly technological medication administration options are often not feasible among older adults¹⁶.

Current evidence suggests that older adults benefit from personal attention when receiving education regarding their medication regimens. Clear instructions accompanied by a concise, accurate medication list were effective at improving medication adherence and knowledge in the primary care setting^{1,5,8,17,22}. Some studies suggest interval follow up phone calls and/or office visits to reinforce medication regimen information improve medication adherence^{5,7}. These findings support the “Back to Basics” approach used in this DNP project.

The purpose of this project was to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy of medication regimens among adults aged 65 and older in a primary care setting. The specific aims were to develop, implement, and evaluate evidence-based activities to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy by encouraging self-management of medication regimens.

Methods

Design

A quality improvement (QI) approach sought to improve knowledge of medications and perceptions of medication self-efficacy in a primary care setting. Quality improvement projects aim to improve the processes or outcomes of care for a given patient group in a particular setting¹⁹.

Model

The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model provided the theoretical underpinnings for this QI project. This model serves to test the implementation of change and is particularly useful in healthcare settings. The PDSA model uses a systematic approach to initiate and evaluate a rapid cycle practice change¹⁴ and serves as the organizational process framework for this project. For this project, the *Plan* stage involved formation of a team, definition of the project aim, and construction of a plan. Administration of the Self-Efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use Scale (SEAMS) and MKAT tools, standardized education, making follow up phone calls, and re-administering both tools at one- and two-month intervals comprised the *Do* stage. Data analysis and documentation of results took place in the *Study* stage. The *Act* stage required the author to decide if findings should be adopted, adapted, or abandoned.

Sample

A convenience sample of 50 participants from the principle author's practice provided the patient sample for this project. Criteria for inclusion were: being age 65 or older, taking four or more prescription medications, scoring 4-5 on the Mini-Cognitive screening tool, residing at home, possessing a phone, speaking English, having the visual ability to read medication lists generated from electronic medical record, and being a

current patient at the project setting. Although consideration for inclusion of patients with a Mini-Cog score below four was dependent upon the willingness of a full-time caregiver to be educated and assist patient, none agreed to participate. Participants were recruited using flyers listing inclusion criteria in the medical office.

Setting

The project took place in an Internal Medicine (IM) office in an urban community setting. The office primarily serves a population living in a retirement community located less than one mile from the office. The majority of patients seen were over 65 years old. The IM office staff consists of a medical doctor (MD), a registered nurse (RN), and a medical assistant (MA).

Procedures

Institutional Review Board (IRB) determination was procured from California State University, Long Beach. Interested participants were screened using the Mini-Cog evaluation tool. Those with scores ≥ 4 received a complete description of the project and were invited to participate. Informed consent was obtained. Signed consents were secured in a separate folder in a locked drawer and participants were assigned a tracking number. Inclusion criteria were verified in the electronic medical record.

Participants completed a baseline survey of self-efficacy and knowledge of medications while the principal author read the items aloud and recorded participants' responses. The principle author provided 20 minutes of standardized education regarding the participants' medication regimens, focusing on specific medication names, doses, schedules, and purposes as well as the importance of having a current medication list at the time of each doctor visit. The principle author made a phone call two days after

baseline education to reinforce details of medication regimen and answer questions. Participants were encouraged to call the office for medication changes, questions, or concerns. Self-efficacy and knowledge of medications were assessed again at one- and two-month intervals. Participants were given the option to complete these assessments face-to-face (F2F) or by phone at the one- and two-month follow up.

Measures

Three measurement tools were used in this project. The Mini-Cog screened for project eligibility. It includes two simple tasks: a three-item word recall exercise and a clock drawing exercise¹⁴. The three-item recall serves to assess memory and the clock drawing assesses executive function and distracts from the item recall. Scores range from 0-5, with scores of 3-5 indicating a low probability of cognitive impairment¹³. A score of ≥ 4 was the cut off for patient inclusion with this project unless there was a caregiver willing to participate. This tool is effective for screening older adults in the primary care setting for cognitive impairments with a sensitivity of 76-99% and specificity of 89-93% with a 95% confidence interval¹⁰.

A multidisciplinary team of experts in health literacy and medication adherence developed the Self-Efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use tool (SEAMS)²⁰. The tool consists of thirteen questions using a Likert scale to indicate their level of confidence in terms of each question: 1 = not confident, 2 = somewhat confident, and 3 = very confident. Items are summed and scores range from 13-39, with higher scores indicating higher levels of self-efficacy for medication adherence²⁰. For example, one item asks: *How confident are you that you can take your medications correctly when you have a busy day planned?* The SEAMS is a reliable and valid tool across literacy levels with

strong internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.89$) and criterion-related validity strongly correlated with medication adherence ($p = .0001$) for the self-efficacy scale²⁰. The SEAMS tool is easy to implement²¹. It also takes little time to score which make this tool useful in the primary care setting.

The Medication Knowledge Assessment Tool (MKAT) was developed by a team of experts to assess the participants' knowledge of the medication name (generic or brand), dose (in mg, mcg, etc.), schedule, and purpose. Participants received one point for each correct answer and an additional point if they carried a current medication list to each office visit. The MKAT served as a simple survey which was used to quantify medication-related knowledge for this project³. Three internists in the medical office reviewed the tool for face validity. No other valid tool to measure medication knowledge which met the project criteria and explicit aims was identified in the literature.

The SEAMS and MKAT were administered at baseline, one-month, and at two-months after a participant received the Back to Basics education. The survey questions were read aloud and the participant's responses were recorded to ensure consistency among participants. Participants had the option to complete the follow up surveys in the office or by phone.

Data Analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 or Excel was used to analyze data. The following information was collected:

- Demographic/clinical data from EMR and participant input
- Medication data (name, dose, schedule, purpose)
- SEAMS, MKAT scores at baseline, one-month, two-months

Aggregate mean scores of SEAMS at baseline, one-month, and two-months were compared. MKAT scores were reported as percentages (number of correct items/total number of items) to facilitate assessment of change between baseline, one-month, and two-month follow up. Measures of central tendency described baseline/clinical characteristics of the sample.

Results

Fifty participants enrolled in the project; there was no attrition at the one- and two-month follow-ups. The mean age was 78.7 years (SD = 7.9), the majority were females (62%) and married (56%). The average number of medications was 8 (See Table 1).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of Sample, N = 50

Gender	Male 38%	Female 62%		
Marital Status	Married 56%	Divorced 10%	Widowed 26%	Single 8%
Age	Minimum 65	Maximum 94	Mean 78.7	SD 8
Number of medications	4	14	8	3

Note. SD = Standard deviation.

At baseline, 34% of participants carried a medication list. After receiving education and follow up phone calls, the percentage increased to 68% and 88% (one- and two-months, respectively). Thus, there was a 158% increase from baseline to two-months. The increase was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 12.12, p = .000$) (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. *Percent Increase in Medication List Possession*

The SEAMS tool demonstrated strong to moderate internal consistency coefficients, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of .82, .81, and .75 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively. The SEAMS scores and the MKAT scores were strongly correlated at one- and two-month follow up supporting the concurrent (construct) validity of the MKAT ($r = .279, p = .05$, one-month; $r = .318, p = .024$, two-months). There was not a statistically significant correlation at baseline ($r = .093, p = .521$) (See Table 2).

Table 2

Comparison of SEAMS Means at Baseline, One-, and Two-month follow up (n = 50)

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	<i>t</i>	Sig
Baseline	1.92	3.00	2.73	.27	7.08*	.000
One-month Follow up	2.23	3.00	2.83	.20		
Two-Month Follow up	2.46	3.00	2.85	.17	6.76**	.000

Note. * = Aggregate mean score Baseline to One-month follow up, ** = Aggregate mean score Baseline to Two-month follow up

The following items, in order, on the SEAMS tool showed the greatest improvement over time: item 11 (*When you are not sure how to take the medication*), item 12 (*When you are not sure what time of day to take your medication*), and item 1 (*When you get a refill of your old medications and some of the pills look different*). SEAMS tool items with the lowest levels of improvement over time were: item 6 (*When you have a busy day planned*) and item 8 (*When no one reminds you to take the medications*). The mean SEAMS scores showed slight improvement of 2.73, 2.83, and 2.85 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively, yet these differences were statistically significant ($p = .000$).

Figure 2. *Percentage Improvements in SEAMS Items: Baseline to 2-month Follow Up*

Participants' knowledge of their medications (MKAT percentage) improved. The improvement was sustained at the two-month follow up at an average of 11%. Mean MKAT percentage scores rose from 79.38% at baseline to 85.24% and 88.12% at one- and two-months respectively (See Figure 3).

Figure 3. *MKAT Scores: Participants' Percentage of Correct Responses: Minimum, Mean, and Maximum.*

Discussion

The purpose of this evidence-based project was to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy among adults aged 65 and older in a primary care setting. Developing, implementing, and evaluating evidence-based activities to improve medication knowledge and self-efficacy were specific aims of this project. Most studies in the literature focused on either medication knowledge or self-efficacy but did not address the importance of addressing both topics among one sample^{12,17,22}.

Older adults value their independence. The simple act of self-managing their medication regimens allows them to gain higher levels of self-efficacy. Medication self-efficacy decreases errors¹ and facilitates the ability to lead independent lives. The SEAMS tool was a reliable assessment tool to gauge self-efficacy for appropriate

medication use as demonstrated by strong to moderate internal consistency coefficients of .82, .81, and .75 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively.

Surprisingly, most participants had high levels of self-efficacy for medication management as indicated by their SEAMS scores at baseline, one-month, and two-months. The following items, in order, on the SEAMS tool showed the greatest improvement over time: item 11 (*When you are not sure how to take the medication*), item 12 (*When you are not sure what time of day to take your medication*), and item 1 (*When you get a refill of your old medications and some of the pills look different*). With standardized education, self-efficacy regarding these areas increased the most among the items. SEAMS tool items with the lowest levels of improvement over time were: item 6 (*When you have a busy day planned*) and item 8 (*When no one reminds you to take the medications*). These areas may have shown little improvement because participants' reported high levels of self-efficacy at baseline and a suspected ceiling effect. Since the majority of participants rated these items higher at baseline, there was little likelihood of improvement.

The MKAT tool was used to assess participants' ability to recall their medication names, doses, schedules, and purposes and to verify if a current medication list was in the participants' possession. Though most participants rated their self-efficacy of medication management high at baseline, many had limited knowledge of their medications. In fact, the majority of participants did not know their correct medication doses. Participants' knowledge of medication doses improved slightly after receiving education about the variety of doses associated with their particular medications. For example, many participants taking atorvastatin were not aware the medication was available in 10mg,

20mg, 40mg, and 80mg doses. In hindsight, it would be beneficial if the data from the MKAT were itemized to examine where the participants' primary weaknesses were in terms of their medication regimens. Also, MKAT scores may have shown only a mild increase due to participants relying on their medication lists rather than learning about their medications.

There was gradual improvement noted when comparing the SEAMS and MKAT scores at baseline, one-month, and two-month intervals. Gradual changes can be seen more frequently among older adults and are particularly characteristic of health behavior changes. Such changes may be more significant if the project took place over a longer length of time. A longer project period may have been more conducive to changing health behavior especially when considering the older adult population and their unique needs. Though the mean SEAMS scores showed only slight improvement of 2.73, 2.83, and 2.85 at baseline, one-month, and two-months respectively, these differences were statistically significant ($p = .000$).

With the mean number of medications being 8, the decreased ability to memorize one's medication regimen is understandable. Thus, possessing a current medication list is of utmost importance to older adults who may not be able to recall every detail of their medication regimen. At baseline, 34% of participants carried a medication list. After receiving education and follow up phone calls, the percentage increased to 68% and 88% (one- and two-months, respectively). Thus, there was a 158% increase from baseline to two-months. The increase was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 12.12, p = .000$).

Implications for Practice

The project findings may be replicable in other care settings. If older adults were able to gain medication knowledge and improve their levels of medication self-efficacy in the primary care setting, they may also benefit from similar approaches in hospital settings or specialists' offices. Other patient populations could receive similar interventions with the same results, if not better. Regardless of age or healthcare setting, all patients could benefit from standardized education regarding their specific medications. Medication errors could decrease and levels of self-efficacy increase. The simple act of providing each patient with a current medication list and encouraging them to bring it to each health care visit would reduce adverse drug events and raise levels of patient safety. It must be noted, however, that initial data collection and education at baseline were time consuming and required longer visits with the patients initially.

Limitations

The small sample size ($n = 50$) and the convenience sample used for this project limit generalizability to other primary care settings. In addition, time constraints further limited recruitment and desired length of follow up (e.g. 6 months). The use of self-report, especially when the principle author read questions aloud and recorded participant responses, could have lead participants to respond favorably (social desirability).

Conclusion

This project showed face-to-face education and provision of an accurate medication list increases medication self-efficacy and knowledge regarding medication regimens in primary care settings. While most studies support either medication adherence or medication knowledge, this project linked the two concepts. Further

projects are needed to investigate different age groups and care settings to ascertain if these findings could translate to different settings and samples. While different teaching strategies may be more beneficial with other age groups and settings, older adults in the primary care setting responded positively to the “back to basics” approach that is based on face-to-face, standardized teaching.

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